

International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research (IJEASR)

ISSN: 2349 –2899 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –4808 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com>

Instructions for authors and subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

Download full paper from:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-5-sep-2014-0>

WORKPLACE UNIVERSITY

Shankar Subramanian Iyer

Senior Business Instructor

National Institute for Vocational Education,
Dubai Academic City, Dubai, UAE

Abstract:

Why do we study or educate oneself, the final outcome is to be employable and apply the skills and learning at the workplace, so it is evident the best place to learn is the workplace. This is undisputable. But the whole problem is the academicians don't have sufficient knowledge, experience and skills to implement this. An Academician has majorly bookish knowledge probably never tested except a handful few who have somehow landed in Academics from the Industry. The Industry does not respect the Academician as he cannot or never had opportunity to apply the skills in the workplace. This is like talking about an experience but never experienced this. At the same time the Industry person has limited knowledge or skills which he/she developed on the job which cannot be quantified as no system exists which can do this. This can be tested by conducting survey and evaluating the survey findings.

Key words: Workplace University, Workplace certification, Vocational skills evaluation , Work skills Quantification

Introduction:

Workplace University- A new concept and my area of Research

The future trend in Education is going to be studying on the job or at the workplace and get credit for this education from prior learning or experience learning which has not been done this date.

Why do we study or educate oneself, the final outcome is to be employable and apply the skills and learning at the workplace, so it is evident the best place to learn is the workplace. This is undisputable. But the whole problem is the academicians don't have sufficient knowledge, experience and skills to implement this. An Academician has majorly bookish knowledge probably never tested except a handful few who have somehow landed in Academics from the Industry. The Industry does not respect the Academician as he cannot or never had opportunity to apply the skills in the workplace. This is like talking about an experience but never experienced this. At the same time the Industry person has limited knowledge or skills which he/she developed on the job which cannot be quantified as no system exists which can do this.

Suppose we have a system where the assessor/teacher can go to the workplace, assess the skills and quantify the same into credits which can be used for further education or further job prospects the system will be massive success. For this we require people who have had sufficient exposure to the teaching/education field and been in the corporate to achieve. Do

we have so many of them and how many of them are keen to go into academics from the industry when the pay scales hardly match?

For example if we consider an Industry Scenario of 10 years, a good performance will be at the level of senior Manager and drawing about 12000 USD per month, but in Academics even if the person is a PhD along with Bachelor, Master's degree would have about 4 years of post-education experience will draw about 5000 USD.

The successful senior Manager has team building skills, leadership qualities, able to set and achieve goals, do research everyday as he has to perform 'customer relationship, satisfaction, find out what works or does not. Whereas the Associate professor has certified Research skills, not enough teaching skills, not enough leadership qualities etc. which is still not proven as he has not applied them.

The current system of separate Industry and Academician qualifications are not helping each other and so Associate professor cannot fit into the Industry nor the senior Manager in the Academic as he does not have masters or PhD. This has been going on for 5-6 decades now. I think the time has come when the two need to merge. The senior Manager should be able to get certified to enter Academics and at the same time the Academician gets exposure to the Industry. This way both the sectors will benefit as the Academics will get the rich exposure to Industrial practices which is required for successful placements and the Industry Manager is able to get certified to grow and come into the education. This way there will exchange of skills, information and knowledge which will improve the society and the world.

Suppose we develop a system where Experienced Assessor goes to the corporate and along with the HR team work out the workplace certification process, like if the senior Manager is just Bachelor in Engineering, and doing the job for 10 years, he definitely is performing as team leader, motivating his team, setting goals, budgets and achieving them this is Management outcomes so the assessor works out the outcomes achievable and learning by performing or doing, vocational and certifies him as Masters in Management by collecting evidence of work certified by supervisor, peer, subordinate, supplier, customer performing this outcome and balance few things/outcomes can be worked out and the senior manager is now Masters in Management. Then look at the benefits

- (I). The time saved for the senior Manager in going to Institutes,
- (II). The society is benefited as one more post graduate
- (III). The company benefits as the skills are certified
- (IV). The employee can go into Academics if he wishes
- (V). The education sector will benefit as the Assessor and the new Post graduate has got rich Industrial experience
- (VI). The money spend and time is minimum
- (VII). The student and Assessor is satisfied and the money involved can be as low as 1/3th the cost of the total cost paid and spend in the education
- (VIII). The assessor and the people concerned can earn more
- (IX). More number of employees can be covered at one time

If a team of 5 Assessors in an Institute approach let us consider 3 organizations like RTA, DEWA, DUBAL. Each Assessor can look at 2-3 learners (the people to be certified) spend 3 hours per sitting working on the outcomes and give guidance and go to another company with 2-3 learners i.e. 6 hours in a day and cover 3 companies with target of 30 learners, the masters will not take more than 1 year at the workplace with major outcomes covered. An institute has 150 corporate learners certified in one year. If this is done in 20 Institutes we have about 3000 post graduates per year which is major record for countries like UAE for Emaritization goals.

I call this as **"WORKPLACE UNIVERSITY"** as Academician outcomes are achieved at the workplace which is just a dream come true for the Education World.

The results are going to be best as this is best participation methodology possible which by research can retain more than 75% of the learning.

How to market education successfully in the UAE (especially to UAE Nationals)

1. Topic of thesis: The Education Industry has been in boom in the UAE for the past decade but the learner outcomes have not be so achievable. It is found that students are graduating but not learning much. This has been the opinion of the Teachers, workplace supervisors and the Industry in general. Learners are first of all not inclined to attending schools, colleges maybe due to their childhood background. But it is not that they lack in skills, intelligence to excel as those who have got interested in the process have managed to excel in the academics and in their profession. Then what are the factors which deter this learning process. The study will involve identifying these factors and suggest feasible solutions to overcome these factors which will help market and reach education to the Learners in the UAE.

This being a grey area generally not discussed much by the people concerned. The educational boom and the UAE desire to be educational HUB of learning is evident by the number of initiatives by the Federal and state governments like Dubai who have special education zones created across UAE. One needs to study the needs of these students, their limitations and then identify the factors which are barrier to their education and find ways of avoiding them to ensure successful education norms which will benefit the majority of the students.

2. Title of the thesis: Marketing Education successfully in the UAE-comparative study with other countries.

3. The scope and coverage of the research study: The research study will identify the major factors which determine the marketing of education in the UAE. The factors will be then analyzed to suggest suitable ways of avoiding or mitigating the effects of these factors.

4. Objectives of the study: To identify the major factors influencing education and marketing of the same in the UAE. Likely factors identified by speaking to experienced people in the Industry, Teaching, education sector and past and present students, potential students also seem to be

- a. Lack of proper formal schooling most of the cases
- b. Enough care not taken at school level to impart education, focus on studies not adequate
- c. Family problems
- d. Distance to travel for studying
- e. Personal tutor, guide required to study and impart knowledge
- f. Personal initiative very low
- g. Time and resources like money lacking
- h. Lack of opportunities to study
- i. Language barrier
- j. Workplace pressure, peer pressure to get graduation or diploma for future promotions
- k. No liking for online studies and prefer one to one with guide
- l. Whether the working learner prefer courses and curriculum which will consider prior learning at workplace to satisfy learning outcomes, this will reduce the burden, stress on the learner

These factors need to be researched further and confirmed to be used by researchers, educators and the Industry to impart future education.

- 5. Sources of data:** Primary data- Teachers Interview, student's interview, Industry personnel Interview, Questionnaire send to sample size 1000 and to be collected and analyzed
Secondary data - government data, university data, Industry data
- 6. Methodology of the study:** study each of the factors as hypothesis or some of the major factors and form hypothesis question and then collect data to analyze the data to either accept or reject the hypothesis using chi square method or using SPSS, present the findings, data collection, analysis with conclusion and summary for the doctoral thesis
- 7. the hypothesis: "the UAE student is not pursuing further education due to above factors"**

Accept or Reject using statistical methods and analysis on the primary data collected
- 8. findings:** Present the data to Audience **along with the data collected, analysis**
- 9. Conclusion and summary:** Summarize the findings and conclusion of the research project and give suggestions for implementing the same.

References:

Website: <http://www.eisneramper.com/A-Workplace-University.aspx>

About the Author: Shankar Subramanian Iyer is Senior Instructor at the National Institute for Vocational Education, Dubai. His area of expertise is developing vocational course Curriculum and imparting vocational skills to learners who have less qualifications but more oriented to workplace. He has 25 years of teaching various Engineering and Business subjects to Learners with various background culturally, education and workplace experience. He has more than 15 years of work Experience in Marketing Industrial, retail, financial products, about 7-8 years of Project Management experience and project funding experience.